

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL-MORAL STEREOTYPES ON THE MANAGEMENT ACTIVITY OF FEMALE LEADERS

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<https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10183590>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th November 2023
Accepted: 21th November 2023
Online: 22th November 2023

KEY WORDS

Public policy, women, the period of new reforms, appointment, election and right to be elected, management system, female leaders, women's public administration, social stereotype.

ABSTRACT

This article talks about the rights of women to appoint, elect and be elected to management positions in the new development stage of today's Uzbekistan, their ability to show their talent in all areas of the national economy, the fact that women are an active subject of the public administration system, social and political existence.

Today, the issue of women has risen to the level of state policy, and in the period of new reforms in Uzbekistan, it is important that their rights to appoint, elect and be elected to management positions are strengthened by law, and that they are recognized not only as an object of studying social issues, but also as having the ability to show their talents in all areas of the national economy. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoyev, stated, "We have determined measures to further strengthen the position of women in state administration. We have increased the share of women in the management system in our country to 33%. In our country, about 1,500 female specialists were appointed to leadership positions at various levels" [1].

In the next stages of socio-historical development, there will be changes in the attitude towards women as a subject of social life, and even doctrines that oppose women and men as antagonists to each other. There are still views that question the fact that a woman has the power and ability to create a socio-political existence, therefore, the "women's issue" attracts the attention of progressive and democratic forces.

We can also find views that reject the social subjectivity of women and ignore their humanity in the work of thinkers, creators, and philosophers who have made a great contribution to human thought. When Homer says, "There is nothing more fatal than a woman," Thales, one of the seven sages and the founder of philosophy, praises that he was not born a woman. Socrates says, "You should fear a woman's love more than a man's anger" [2]. And Aristophanes describes the women who want to take over management with funny expressions [3]. We can find such thoughts in the works of Buddha, Confucius, Plato, Aristotle, Schopenhauer, Nietzsche. The most surprising thing is that, in accordance with the increase in

the role and position of men in the political life, negative attitude towards the role of women in social life has expanded. When a man appeared on the stage of socio-historical development as the main subject of property relations, it became common to limit the rights and freedoms of a woman. Solon's order that "a woman thinks nothing of ruling, for her it is necessary to play the role of wife, servant and helper" [4] became widespread in the following centuries. Only in the 19th century, an organized mass movement began to restore women's human rights, to free them from various forms of violence, discrimination and inhuman customs, and the necessary norms were adopted at the international level [5]. In this regard, J.A. Condorcet ("On the Introduction of Women to Civil Rights"), Olympia de Gouges and Louise Lacolibe ("Women's Right", Codex), T.G. von Gippel ("On the Improvement of the Civil Status of Women") we can recall the socio-political performances of Later, feminist movements in North America, New Zealand, Australia, Finland, Norway, Sweden, England, Germany, and Austria ensured that women had full political rights in the 20th century [6].

The functioning of women as a subject in the system of public administration is closely related to the functions before social and political institutions. When women participate in the state management system, they must first of all be well aware of the functional features of this management system and the technology of their implementation.

Since the main principle of a democratic state is to serve people, it is undoubtedly obliged to take into account the needs and requirements of all objects. Therefore, women, both as objects and as people, put their demands and needs before the management, and want their satisfaction. This creates the basis for them to set certain tasks to the public administration system as an object, that is, they bring their functions to the management system. In our opinion, these tasks consist of the functions arising from the following social and demographic status of women.

1. Ensuring the socio-political, economic and cultural rights of women.
2. Establishing gender equality in the family, fight against discrimination.
3. Greater involvement of women in the management of state and community affairs.
4. Help to improve the management system.
5. To achieve the development of civil institutions.
6. Contribute to the education of the young generation by organizing spiritual and educational events.

It can be seen that with these functions, women help the public administration system to fully fulfill social tasks, and even take over some of its functions.

The state management system of women and girls has a cratological essence (state significance) as an active subject of socio-political existence. When the new state administration system is being formed, the social and political activity of citizens, the role of democratic values in the decision-making is of incomparable importance.

In the speech of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev at the 20th plenary session of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis, we quote the views of the UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres (report at the 63rd session of the UN Commission on the Status of Women held on March 11-17, 2019, in which the delegation of our country also participated), acknowledged that "where women are actively participating in political and social life, the economy grows, stability is strengthened, and the well-being of citizens increases" [7].

The state policy in Uzbekistan to protect the rights and interests of women, to achieve full participation of women in the social and political life of the country, to ensure gender equality, to protect reproductive health, is supported by the international community, in particular, the United Nations, the International Labor Organization, UNICEF, the World Health Organization. It is highly rated by prestigious international specialized institutions such as the Organization for Conservation of Nature. ... it was emphasized that such positive changes, first of all, are the solid foundation of our important work aimed at increasing the social prestige of women in our country [8].

Women's rights, such as liberating women from the view that they are excluded from the management of society, working equally with men in the society without giving up the responsibilities of motherhood and wifehood, receiving adequate wages, health care, education, voting and being elected, began to manifest themselves more strongly since the 20th century.

According to S.T. Inomova, a scientist of women's activity, the meaning of the national policy is to turn the state policy aimed at the social support of women into the work of the whole community [9].

Today, in the new stage of development of our country, the demand for management personnel has significantly increased in the country, the implementation of personnel training, qualification improvement and retraining mechanisms for the newly independent state, first of all, the improvement of the qualifications of the existing personnel in the management and government structures has been defined as a necessary task. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev said, "At the same time, a system is being created to prepare socially active women for leadership positions, to train them and improve their qualifications. All this shows that the women's movement in our country has great potential and prospects [10]".

From this point of view, it is studied as a socio-psychological problem that the issue of personnel is subordinated to a certain department in the administration system, that it is defined as their main task as an organizational issue, that the principle of equality in the issue of personnel selection for the management system (the criteria are applied equally to women and men, gender inequality) does not work.

It is known that under the influence of "modernization" of society, the role of women in society, their political, cultural, legal views and behavior have changed a lot. In particular, women began to find their place in the society along with raising children in the family and serving their husbands. Stereotypes and norms of activity were formed in women.

Changes in the political processes in countries, the civilization of cities, and the role of women in economic reforms began to be clearly felt. Women became active not only in working with the family, but also in social life. In particular, various foundations and societies were created by women, and they began to express themselves in political activities. Women united around non-governmental, non-profit organizations, political parties and had the opportunity to solve their own problems.

The psychological characteristics and abilities of women began to show themselves with their social adaptation, leaving the norms of social stereotypes. The emergence of the possibility of women being paid for their work and contributing to the family budget not only

solved financial issues in the family and society, but also played an important role in the formation of self-confidence, respect, incentives and motives.

For example, in the mid-70s and early 80s, representatives of the field of social philosophy and sociology began to study the problems of women and men.

It can be concluded that, first of all, it is necessary to create conditions for women to show activity in management. This is seen in provisioning, enabling, support, experience, competence, skill building.

Secondly, in the personnel reserve, a person is prepared for a specific position at a certain time. In it, special skills are formed and, of course, an appointment to management is made. The "legitimacy" of using the personnel reserve is realized when the personnel included in the reserve fully feel that they are being prepared for a specific position, when they perform tasks seriously, when they approach the study of documents related to the field responsibly, and when they can defend their opinion.

Thirdly, it is necessary to pay attention to the immanent signs and take into account intuition in the active application of the institution of the formation of the female personnel reserve in practice and success. Stress resistance and emotional stability should be recognized as a positive feature in women's activities, especially in management.

Fourthly, when selecting a candidate, the leader must have accurate information about the social-psychological, emotional-emotional characteristics and abilities of the women included in the personnel reserve. It increases the reliability of proper orientation of activities, planning, expectation of results.

Fifth, using the potential of women with high risk-taking ability in the economic sphere will have a positive effect. Along with risk-taking, women's orderly-organizational qualities are also of great importance. Discipline in activity is mainly seen in decision-making, determination in interpersonal and inter-organizational relations, and this has a positive effect on the organization's image and economic potential.

Sixth, it is an effective way to pay special attention to the development of communication and empathic skills, especially in women, in the selection of personnel in the social sector. When working with the public, it is necessary to take into account the level of communication and empathy in communicating, listening, and establishing a relationship with the middle class of the population, in need of social protection. These skills have a positive impact on employment, labor, health, and poverty reduction. From this point of view, empathy in women is not a negative aspect, but an effective tool for solving social problems.

Seventh, the activity of women who fit the type of "innovative leader" and "executive leader" will have a good effect in the fields whose activities are directly related to international relations and international image. This is evident in the searchability of the staff, motivational approach, effective use of immanent features.

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